

Exploring Reaction Time Distributions Through Hierarchical Bayesian Models

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Test Fatigue: Laboratory Experiments

- Basic cognitive experiments control both encoding and retrieval phases
- Repeated measures offer a method of increasing measurement precision
- Extending the encoding/retrieval phase can paradoxically increase measurement error
 - Introduces cognitive fatigue and related nuisance variables
 - Reduces accuracy
 - Increases response time (variability)

Test Fatigue: Testing and Assessment

- Can only control retrieval factors
- Lengthening tests offers a method of increasing measurement precision of latent traits
- Might potentially produce similar paradoxically increases in measurement error
 - Introduces cognitive fatigue and related nuisance variables
- Assessments that depend on reaction times might produce biased estimates

Addressing Fatigue

- Modifying experimental design / assessment
 - Shorting retrieval tasks
 - Promote reaction time tasks to beginning of assessments
- Control via statistical methods

Research Goals

- Investigate systematic reaction time patterns as a function of test serial position
- Descriptively compare two models
 - Hierarchical IRT approach
 - Weibull distribution with shift parameter

H - IRT

Weibull

Estimate Comparison

Conclusions

- Both models led to similar conclusions
- H-IRT advantages
 - Estimate correlation between variables in sub-models
 - Bayes factors normally distributed, better for hyper-effects
- Weibull advantages
 - Estimating interaction of ability and other covariates
 - Shift parameter to control for quickest reactions

